

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PUBLICATION OF ARTISTIC WORKS ON THE THEME OF KARABAKH (BASED ON AFLATUN BAKSHALIYEV'S BOOK "KARABAKH IS AZERBAIJAN")

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Abstract

The Karabakh region occupies an important place in Azerbaijani literature due to its historical and cultural significance. Since the end of the 20th century, this theme has gained particular prominence in poetry and prose. Works that focus on Karabakh reflect themes of national identity, the struggle for freedom and the region's cultural heritage in poetic language. Aflatun Bakshaliyev's book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" is one of the remarkable works that presents the Karabakh theme with historical and emotional depth. The author emphasises the motifs of homeland, land and heroism, skilfully expressing Karabakh's culture and history through poetry. The book, published by the "Elm və Təhsil" publishing house in 2023, highlights certain aspects related to the alignment of content and design during the publication process. The depiction of leaves on the cover limits the symbolism of an open sky, which represents freedom. It is recommended to reduce the size of the leaves and give more space to the depiction of the gates of Shusha Fortress. Placing the author's name below the flag illustration would harmonise with the national symbolism. In addition, replacing the Cyrillic inscription "Шыша" on the gates with its Latin script version "Şuşa" would be in keeping with contemporary standards. The back cover could also benefit from a more detailed presentation of the author's biography, which would enhance the book's scholarly and educational value.

The book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" is a valuable contribution to the promotion of the Karabakh theme in Azerbaijani literature. Improving its design and content aspects would further enhance its ability to effectively convey Karabakh's cultural heritage and the idea of freedom to readers. This work has not only literary, but also national and cultural significance.

Keywords: imaginative literature, Karabakh conflict, publication process, poet.

The Karabakh region also occupies an important place in fiction due to its turbulent history, rich cultural heritage and the role it plays in the national consciousness of the Azerbaijani people (Sharifova, 2022). The theme of Karabakh has been reflected in our literature for many years. Famous poets and writers of Azerbaijan always describe in their works the fascinating nature of Karabakh, historical events and heroes that took place there. Since the end of the twentieth century, this theme has occupied a special place in poetry and prose. The works reflect the history, culture, customs and traditions of Karabakh, the struggle for the liberation of these lands from Armenian occupation.

The subject of the study is the description of the Karabakh region in fiction and the process of editing and publishing Aflatun Bakshaliyev's book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan". The main focus is on how the book presents the Karabakh issue in a poetic way, how the poet expresses the historical and emotional burden, as well as the compatibility of content and form. At the same time, the purpose of this study is to consider the quality of publication, design and editing of the work, and to highlight the cultural and historical significance of the works written on the Karabakh theme (Science.gov.az, n.d.).

The book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" by the famous poet Aflatun Bakshaliyev is a valuable artistic work in which the author expresses the spirit, culture and historical significance of the Karabakh region in poetic language. Through the poems contained in the book, the poet has written down the sorrows, joys and historical memory of Karabakh. In poetic language, the author masterfully expresses the emotional charge and

cultural values of the region. Each poem is filled with deep feelings and thoughts about the nature and people of Karabakh. In the poet's work, the motifs of motherland, land, leader and personality, people and army, heroism are in the foreground. Poems such as "This road leads us to Karabakh", "Great Saviour", "I am from Karabakh", "Victory is yours", "Azerbaijan land", "To the martyrs of the Second Karabakh War" are sincerely expressed with boundless devotion and love for the country (Bakshaliyev, 2023).

Using poetic images and symbols, the poet brings the reader closer to the cultural heritage of Karabakh. In terms of content and structure, the book consists of different poems, and each poem illuminates a different aspect of Karabakh.

We would like to take into account some points related to the publication, compilation and editing of Aflatun Bakshaliyev's book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan".

The book was published in 2023 by the "Science and Education" publishing house in Baku, with a print run of 300 copies. Director of the publishing house Inal Mammadov, editor-in-chief PhD philologist, associate professor Gunay Garayeva supported the publication of this book and hoped that it would take its place in the literary environment. Technical editor Rovshana Nizamigizi and designer Zahid Mammadov worked hard to give the book an aesthetic appearance.

Associate Professor Alizadeh Askerli, who holds a doctorate in philology, wrote an interesting preface to the book. Here he named the poems of various genres written by the poet in the course of his work, gave examples of them, talked about their artistic merits (Bakshaliyev, 2023).

In this book, which has 308 pages in total, the number of sheets indicated corresponds to the actual number of sheets. Unfortunately, in some publications these data do not coincide, the number of sheets marked with the number of sheets available in the publication is different (Valiyev, 2009).

The protective and aesthetic function of the book cover is one of the main design principles of modern publications. Although the book cover in this example is made of rich colours and hard material, there are certain aesthetic and thematic shortcomings in the design elements.

One of the main elements that stands out on the cover of the book is the image of leaves reaching up to the sky. These leaves, as part of the surrounding landscape, limit the image of the fortress gate of the city of Shusha and visually obstruct the image of the open sky that symbolises the free sky of Karabakh. However, the freedom of Karabakh is symbolised precisely by the clear and open sky. In this regard, if the use of leaves is not mandatory, it would be advisable to reduce their scale or place them in the second plan of the composition (Knyaz, 2015).

The limited space allocated to the Shusha city gate and the fact that the image is not fully expressed in the design do not adequately reflect the cultural and historical significance of Karabakh. In this context, it is recommended that the image of the Shusha City Gate be given more space and presented as a more dominant design element.

The image of the flag of Azerbaijan on the cover of the book is presented as a special design element. However, placing the author's name above the description of the flag violates the principle of ethical compliance. In order to maintain the supremacy of national symbols, the author's name should be placed below the flag or in an inconspicuous place (Valiyev, 2009). This would be both an indicator of respect for national values and maintain the balance of the design. In addition, the Cyrillic writing of the word 'Шыша' on the castle gate creates a thematic contradiction in the proposed layout. Considering that the book was published in 2023, it would be more appropriate to write this inscription in the Latin alphabet 'Şuşa' according to the graphic rules of modern times. Especially after the Second Karabakh War in 2020, Karabakh and its cities have become important symbols of national identity.

The back of the book contains a photograph of the author and a short biography. Although this information is a useful addition for readers wishing to become acquainted with the author's work, it is recommended that it be presented in a more comprehensive and detailed form. For example, the inclusion of specific information about the author's literary career and creative process will increase the reader's interest and increase the scientific-didactic value of the book (Valiyev, 2009).

In order to increase the overall aesthetic and content relevance of the book, the following suggestions are made:

1.Placement of design elements: The clear sky image should dominate rather than the leaves closing

the sky. If the use of leaves is necessary, it is advisable to place them on a smaller scale and at the edges.

2.The advantage of national symbols: The author's name should be placed at a distance of at least 1.5-2 cm below the flag. This distance should be at least 1 cm for small books.

3.Optical centre layout: The title of the book should be placed in the optical centre, not the geometry of the page. This is more in line with the visual perception of the reader's eye.

4.Graphic Writing Style: Writing the word "Shusha" on the gate of Shusha Castle in the Latin alphabet is more in line with modern design standards.

5.Expanding the background: The information presented about the author in a more detailed and readable form will increase the scientific and cultural value of the book.

Book design is not only a visual presentation, but also a means to convey the message of the content more effectively (Knyaz, 2017). The design approach, which keeps Karabakh's freedom, national values and historical symbols in the foreground, enhances the aesthetic quality and attracts the reader's attention. The introduction of the proposed changes will greatly enhance both the visual and thematic power of the book.

In general, the book "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" occupies a special place in our literature among the works written on national, social and historical issues. Its publication is a valuable contribution to the lovers of literature as a part of the literature written about Karabakh.

At the same time, we should not forget that the publication and editing of fiction on Karabakh occupies an important place in Azerbaijani culture (Knyaz, 2017). The Karabakh conflict and its consequences are a very complex issue from an emotional and historical point of view. Therefore, the sensitive preparation and editing of works written on the Karabakh issue for publication is very important (Sharifova, 2022). Both authors and editors should pay special attention to the works written on this topic, both in terms of language and content.

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